

ISic3401

I.Sicily inscription 3401

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

list

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Ortygia, from demolition of 16th cent. fortifications at entrance to
island

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 7261

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140300

1. Ζωτικός,
2. Δέκομος,
3. Εύκτῆμ[ω]ν,
4. Ὀνάσιμος,
5. [Φιλ]ήμων
- 6.

Edition: PHI336190

1. [οἱ ἔφηβοι οἱ στεφανωθέντες(?)]
2. Ζωτικός [τοῦ δεῖνος]
3. Δέκομος [τοῦ δεῖνος]
4. Εύκτῆμων [τοῦ δεῖνος] ²EYKTHMON, facs., Orsi²
5. Ὀνάσιμος [τοῦ δεῖνος]
6. [(?)Φιλ]ήμων [— — —]
7. [— — — — — — —]

8.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644946

PHI 140300

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Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0009a (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 49.1331.3

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità.* At 371

Manganaro, G. 1999. Sikelika: studi di antichità e di epigrafia della Sicilia greca. Pisa, Roma. At 67 no.59 fig.141

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